

GREEN SCENT

SMART CITIZEN EDUCATION FOR A GREEN FUTURE

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PARTNERS

UNIVERSITÀ TELEMATICA INTERNAZIONALE UNINETTUNO

DEMOCRACY X
TECHNOLOGY, SOCIETY & SUSTAINABILITY

ENGINEERING

in Transylvania

Barcelona Supercomputing Center
Centro Nacional de Supercomputación

Maunulan yhteiskoulu
HELSINGIN MATEMATIIKKALUKIO

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UAB

Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

ELLINOGERMANIKI AGOGI

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European Certification & Qualification Association

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GREENSCENT

Our objective

GreenSCENT - Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future - aims to educate and empower the people of Europe to change their behaviour towards the environment by fostering empathy for the planet.

WWW.GREEN-SCENT.EU

GREENSCENT BOX

Through collaboration and research-based learning, GreenSCENT developed digital, physical and hybrid educational tools and activities that can be used to promote environmental awareness.

OPEN INNOVATION CHALLENGES

GreenSCENT organised three Open Innovation Challenges, open to citizens, students, and start-ups across Europe. The goal was to develop new projects that rethink how food is produced, transported, and consumed in Europe.

GREENAIR APPLICATION

The GreenAir application serves as an educational tool on the fundamental concepts behind air quality. It is a web-based app that integrates augmented reality (AR) and gamification features.

CLEANAIR@SCHOOLS

CleanAir@School serves as an educational resource to enhance students' understanding of air pollution and its effects on health. In this experiment, students use NO2 passive sensors to analyse the air quality in their areas after participating in preliminary teaching activities.

CLIMATHON

The Climathon activity is an online course tailored for PhD students and postdocs to delve into climate data analysis together with experts in the field.

CITIZEN SCIENCE: MICROPLASTICS

The microplastics activity aims to increase students' awareness of the issue of microplastics in our waterways. This hands-on activity allows them to explore this emerging phenomenon and develop a deeper understanding of the problem in our oceans.

YOUTH DESIGN ASSEMBLIES

Over the time span of 1,5 years, 58 young people from all over Europe discussed, exchanged ideas, and helped shape a European future focused on the environment, the climate and sustainability. The Youth Design Assemblies convened in online and in person meetings in Spain, Serbia, Italy, and Denmark.

CITIZEN JOURNALISM PLATFORM

The citizen journalism platform allows collecting information, monitoring and reporting environmental issues or solutions about a specific area or territory.

GREENVERSE PLATFORM

By using 360 video technologies, the GreenSCENT platform allows teachers and educators to create 360 environmental video experiences.

GREENSCENT COMPETENCE FRAMEWORK

GreenSCENT developed a competence framework that embraces all areas of the Green Deal through a participatory and learning-by-doing design-based approach.

GREEN LICENCE

GreenSCENT elaborated the ECCEL: a European "driving licence" for Climate and Environmental competences and skills.

EXPLORE MORE

COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION HIGHLIGHTS

The GreenSCENT project has achieved significant milestones in terms of communication and dissemination activities.

The European Green Deal in Education

Published by Routledge, the **European Green Deal in Education** showcases the results of the GreenSCENT project. It provides practical guidance on using digital tools and engaging diverse audiences in sustainability initiatives, making it a valuable resource for students, scholars, and practitioners.

Lulù: The communication barrier breaker board game

Lulù: The communication barrier breaker is an educational board game modelled after the classic Game of Goose. It aims to raise awareness of accessibility in communication and information.

Special Issue in Springer Journal

As an output of the first edition of the Green Digital Accessibility conference in 2022, we published a Special Issue with the Springer journal **Universal Access in the Information Society** (Q2)

GreenSCENT Storytelling Toolkit

The **GreenSCENT storytelling toolkit** empowers children to create their own stories using GreenSCENT characters. This child-centric approach fosters creativity and imagination. To enhance the experience, the toolkit incorporates stop-motion animation techniques, guided by instructional videos.

GreenSCENT Communication Kit

The **GreenSCENT Communication Toolkit** aims to make climate advocacy accessible to everyone, especially people with disabilities. By providing practical guidelines like using alt text, colour contrast, and accessible formats, the toolkit empowers content creators and activities to make their climate communication inclusive and understandable to all.

The Youth Design Assemblies Guide

Engaging young people in shaping the future is crucial for creating relevant, inclusive, and sustainable solutions. To account for this the GreenSCENT project developed **The Youth Design Assembly (YDA)**, providing a structured, participatory method for involving youth in co-creating the GreenSCENT outcomes. A guide to help others use this method can be found [here](#) which offers practical steps for implementing YDAs across various issues to harness the unique insights and experiences of youth in your project.

GREENSCENT AT A GLANCE

GreenSCENT has piloted innovative tools to inspire positive environmental actions across diverse demographics. Here are some key takeaway figures of the project's impact.

6995

People engaged in GreenSCENT piloting activities

GreenSCENT Articles

Over the last 36 months, **27 academic articles** have been published, aiming to provide significant contributions to the areas of environmental education, education for sustainable development, smart accessible environmental education, sustainability, and accessibility.

GreenSCENT Resources

- **5 GreenAir resources**
- **7 reports and guidelines** (Youth Design Assemblies)

GreenSCENT Policy Papers

GreenSCENT published three policy papers:

[Designing Environmental Education with Young People for Young People](#)

[Leaving no one behind in Environmental education](#)

[Towards Transformative and Emancipatory Pedagogies](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036480

GreenSCENT Events

GreenSCENT has been showcased at **29 high-level events** and **73 general events**.

Additionally, GreenSCENT has organised three major conferences under the **Green Digital Accessibility (GDA)** series:

- GDA 2022
- GDA 2023
- GDA 2024

These conferences focus on key themes, including **accessible environmental education, accessibility, and the Just Transition**.

Standardisation

GreenSCENT contributed to the UN's ITU Focus Group on the Metaverse by creating the report "**Accessibility in a Sustainable Metaverse**". This report highlights the importance of inclusivity for all users, including those with disabilities, by emphasising the integration of accessibility features from the initial design phase. It also promotes sustainable technologies focusing on energy efficiency, reduced e-waste, and responsible AI and VR development.